

Value Inculcations in Teacher Education

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ABSTRACT

Obscurantism, fanaticism, violence, superstition and fatalism have been the bane of Indian society and unfortunately, despite the rapid strides we have made in various fields, these obstacles to progress still hold away undermining the unity and integrity of our country. Only awareness and education can banish these ills, which have been corroding our society and universal and internal values for centuries. This context, the role of teacher can not be under-valued.

In a global scenario of erosion of values, it would be difficult to have individuals in society who would strive to halt the process of value deterioration, unless and until schools produce young persons with the right aims and objectives of human life. This should also give clear indication of what should be the curriculum of education in years to come and how the same can contribute in developing the culture of peace within the communities, amongst religious, countries and eventually globally.

The paper will present concept of Value Education Socialized Techniques/approaches incidental learning method effective steps to inculcate values, what must a teacher do.

INTRODUCTION

Obscurantism, fanaticism, violence, superstition and fatalism have been labour. Moral and spiritual training is an essential part of education. if education is to help us to meet moral the bane of Indian society and unfortunately ,despite the rapid strides we have made in various fields, these obstacles to progress still hold away undermining the unity and integrity of our country. Only universal and internal values for centuries this alone can sustain culture and civilization. The true meaning of education is

harmonious development of head, hand, heart i.e., enlightenment of mind, compassion and dignity of challenges of the age and play its part in the life of the community, it should be liberating and life giving. This context, the role of teacher can not be under-valued.

Socialized Techniques/approaches

A variety of group oriented techniques may be used in value education. In simulation activities the learner pretends to be in real situation and portrays events and characteristics in the situation. Modelling is a strategy in which qualities of an individual who is considered to posses desirable or ideal values worth emulating and presented to the learners as a model a broad indication of the kinds of activities possible under the heads of socialized strategies for value education purpose are listed below:

- a. Dramatization activities like staging play, dramas, both of traditional folk and modern on value themes.
- b. Enacting opportunities to take up and practice the role of different kinds taking the role form epics/scriptures.
- c. Modelling exercise, the ideal persons and groups on themes such as
 - 1) Gender inequality
 - 2) Problems pertaining to women's role and education
 - 3) Caring animals and human beings
 - 4) Problem related to environmental protection
 - 5) Consequences of air water pollution

(Constructing the image through discussions, questioning and developing awareness about the specific problems in the above mentioned areas)

Incidental learning method

An incidental is an episode or experience in the life of an individual or group. The incidental approach has a very good point in its favour in that it can be used both inside as well as outside the classroom for value education purpose. It consists in identifying the wrong or right actions of individual or group, either pre-planned to occur or observed by accident, and reprimanding or rewarding those concerned. Several attempts have been made to involve methodologies suitable to the development of value in children and youth. Douglas Suprenant (1976) outlines eight different approaches to value Education, which may be briefly stated as under:

- (1) Evocation Approach: The students are encouraged to make spontaneously free, non-rational choices, without thought or hesitation. It provides an environment which allows maximum freedom for students and provide a provocative situation for which spontaneous reactions are elicited.
- (2) Inculcation Approach: students are forced to act according to specific desired values. A positive and negative reinforcement by the teacher helps value inculcation.
- (3) Awareness Approach: this approach helps students to become aware and identify their own values. The students are encouraged to share their experiences. The teacher presents value laden situations or dilemmas through readings, films, role playing, small group discussions and simulation.
- (4) Moral reasoning approach: Kohlberg's theory of six stages of moral development is the framework most frequently used in this approach. The teacher set up learning experiences which will facilitate moral development.
- (5) Analysis approach: the group and individuals are encouraged to study social value problem. They are asked to clarify value questions and identify values in conflict. They are encouraged to determine the truth and evidence of purported facts and arrive at decision applying analogous cases, inferring and testing value principles underlying the decision.

(6) Value clarification approach: it helps students to use both rational thinking and emotional awareness to examine personal behaviour patterns and classify and actualized values.

(7) Commitment approach: It enables the students to perceive themselves not merely as passive reactor or as free individuals but as inner-related members of a social group and system.

(8) The union approach: the purpose is to help students to perceive themselves and act not as separate egos but as part of a larger inner-related whole the human race, the world, the cosmos.

Effective steps to inculcate values

In the world which is primarily torn between a few 'haves' and majority of 'have-nots' in a highly disproportionate manner, tensions, diversities, inner-division, violence, terrorism, consumerism and the like are creating a dreadful scenario. Education can be the only hope. Education can contribute immensely to a culture of peace, cohesion and collaboration. Twentieth century has given very clear signals to the human race that it must initiate all round efforts to achieve peace as the only other alternative is in the annihilation of human race from the face of the earth.

Education for peace and for a culture of peace is being globally accepted and adopted by the nations and more so by the education systems worldwide. The implications and imperatives need to be understood in right perspectives. In India, the social cohesion adherence to moral and ethical values and commitment to the society have been the hallmark of socio culture ethos. The need to sustain this ethos in the emerging context has been highlighted in the reports of various committees and commissions on education.

What must a Teacher Do

The teacher's comprehension should be extend only to transmitting information from a prescribed textbook to the children but in developing capabilities to involve the curriculum from the surrounding itself at the primary stage of school education. In developing such an approach, the critically need for the value inculcation and emphasis on ethical and moral education should form an integral part of each and every unit and activity. Small stories from epics, mythologies and history suitable to the stage and linked to the value inculcation, would generate

interest amongst the young learners and could familiarise them with the culture evolution and heritage. This would also lead to understanding of the culture and heritage of different communities and gradually help in developing respect for religions, languages and culture practices which may be different from that being practiced and involved in the learners home surroundings. Learning must lead the social cohesion, spirit of co-operation and willingness to work in a group. It could also lead to inculcation of desire to work with others. The school must established mutuality with the communities in various ways, particularly in nurturing in the children this spirit. Communities and individuals would value education more and more in future. They would also assess the returns that they are receiving. A couple of action points could possibly contribute effectively.

Teacher preparation must ensure development of commitment amongst teachers. It is a tough proposition when most of the other sectors are influenced by self interests and material pursuits everywhere. However, teacher education needs to emphasis throughout in its programme that teachers alone can kindle the spirit of value-based growth and development and motivate other to lead their life with full commitment and adherence to common values as imbibed in the constitution of India.

With all the limitations, deficiencies and rigidities inherent in our education system and functioning of the schools and other learning centres, transformation and overhaul of the system has to be achieved only through the combined efforts of the teachers and the communities. A value based approach must form the backbone of educational system and also the teacher education system. Effective and visible steps need to be launched by the teacher education institutions and motivated schools at the earliest. The multiplier effects would be tremendous.

CONCLUSION

In a global scenario of erosion of values, it would be difficult to have individuals in society who would strive to halt the process of value deterioration, unless and until schools produced young persons with the right aims and objectives of human life. This should also give clear indication of what should be the curriculum of education in years to come and how the same can contribute in developing the culture of peace within the communities among religions, countries and eventually globally. The trend of focussing only

on specified examination oriented subject areas need to be described.

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